
ChainBench: An LLM Benchmark for Cross-Chain Code Generation

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Abstract

AI agents are increasingly capable of repository-scale software work, and smart-contract engineering is a particularly high-stakes setting where toolchains and tests enforce correctness. We introduce **ChainBench**, a benchmark for cross-chain smart contract translation and contract generation built from production repositories and their real verification suites. Each task provides a structured specification and containerized environment: systems implement missing functionality to pass the existing verification suite, and are scored by **Pass@1** task success. ChainBench contains **42** tasks spanning **EVM Solidity, NEAR Rust, Aptos Move, Sui Move, and Starknet Cairo**. In a zero-shot evaluation of nine deployed model-agent systems, including both standardized same-harness runs and preferred-harness runs where available, the best achieves **88.1%** success, while several open-weight systems reach **52%–60%** with substantially longer solve times. Performance further varies by target chain and task type, with failures ranging from narrow behavioral mismatches (e.g., missing edge-case guards) to build and repository-compatibility issues.

1. Introduction

AI systems are getting meaningfully better at writing software, and the center of gravity has shifted from chat-based assistance toward agentic systems that can complete larger chunks of work with less supervision. At the same time, autonomous agents are starting to participate in real economic activity—holding wallets, making payments, and purchasing services—and early products are emerging that treat agents as first-class economic participants. In an *agentic economy*, agents that manage treasuries, coordinate resources, or execute strategies will require programmable agreements: code that specifies permissions, invariants, and

settlement logic in a verifiable way. Blockchains provide a natural substrate for these agreements, and smart contracts are the mechanism by which they become enforceable.

This creates a practical and safety-critical question: what can today’s models *actually* do when faced with real smart contract engineering work? Smart contracts already secure large amounts of value, and small implementation errors can lead to catastrophic loss. Recent benchmarks and studies have begun to quantify model capabilities in smart contract domains (e.g., Solidity generation and vulnerability discovery), but we extend this evaluation to core primitives in enterprise-grade development and broader chain/language coverage. In doing so, we measure how models handle smart contract development under real tests across diverse chains. Teams routinely maintain the same protocol across multiple chains with fundamentally different execution models and languages (e.g., EVM/Solidity, Move-based chains such as Sui and Aptos, and non-EVM environments such as Starknet and NEAR). For models intended to accelerate or automate blockchain development, cross-chain translation and end-to-end correctness under production test suites are first-order requirements.

We present **ChainBench**, a benchmark and evaluation framework designed to measure model performance on blockchain development tasks across this spectrum. ChainBench is built from production smart contract repositories and their real test suites, enabling evaluation by running the same tests used by engineers in practice. The initial focus is *cross-chain translation*: a model is given (i) a complete implementation on a source chain and (ii) a partial implementation (scaffolding) on a target chain, and must implement missing functions or modules so that the target repository’s tests pass. By progressively varying task scope—from single, heavily contextualized functions to complete modules and ultimately entire suites with minimal initial support—ChainBench produces a capability curve that tracks progress toward autonomy.

Beyond translation, ChainBench is designed to incorporate tasks along the broader lifecycle needed for autonomous agents: generating contracts from specifications, generating tests and achieving coverage, and verifying or enforcing security-relevant properties. We additionally motivate an industry consortium model: cross-chain deployments are not unique to any one organization, and a shared benchmark

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with contributions of contracts and tests from multiple stakeholders can both improve representativeness and reduce benchmark overfitting. In doing so, we hope to encourage the development of more robust and comprehensive smart contracts to make Web3 more secure.

2. Related Work

Code generation tasks are a common class of LLM benchmarks. Foundation model families like GPT-5 (Singh et al., 2025) and Claude-Opus-4 (Anthropic, 2025) report scores on model cards to showcase a model’s general coding capabilities. HumanEval (Chen et al., 2021) measured the ability to generate individual functions, while modern benchmarks like SWE-bench (Jimenez et al., 2024) and Terminal-bench (Merrill et al., 2026) target more typical development tasks, such as repository-level fixes on GitHub and command line tasks. Typically, these benchmarks focus on self-contained tasks; however, blockchain development requires interaction with an ever-changing open-source state. Smart contracts coordinate activity on a decentralized network of computers. Therefore, code needs to be correct, useful, and secure in the context of network activity.

Most smart contract benchmarks focus on Solidity, the language used for EVM chains. SolContractEval (Ye et al., 2026) measures an LLM’s ability to generate fully-functional smart contracts from complete context dependencies and a structured contract framework. SolEval (Peng et al., 2025) focuses on repository-level tasks for smart contract generation. In addition to compilation and correctness, they include measures for both gas usage and vulnerability with pass@k. EVMBench (Wang et al., 2026) focuses on the ability of AI agents to detect, patch, and exploit different vulnerabilities within smart contracts. While this is great for EVM-compatible chains, many enterprise-grade blockchain applications need cross-chain support. Developers often need to replicate smart contracts across Solidity, Rust, and other languages.

Transcoder (Lachaux et al., 2020) established the foundational pipeline for translating between programming languages when parallel data is scarce. The CodeTransOcean (Yan et al., 2023) benchmark provides a comprehensive testing suite for code translation, but it does not include Solidity or smart contract tasks. ChainBench addresses the gap in the literature by bringing code translation to cross-chain smart contract development. Specifically, it provides a robust testing suite to measure an LLM’s ability to both generate smart contracts from scratch and translate existing smart contracts to another chain/language given full context dependencies and a structured framework.

3. Benchmark Design

ChainBench measures the case where a user has either an industry-grade specification for generation tasks or an existing correct implementation for translation tasks. This led to the following design principles:

1. **Validity** – Generated smart contracts were tested against integration and error tests for the smart contract in the target language. This allowed us to ensure functionality within generated smart contracts despite potential design differences.
2. **Reliability** – We ran a total of 42 tasks and report 95% confidence intervals for the observed benchmark scores.
3. **Coverage** – Benchmark tasks translate smart contracts from EVM to both EVM-compatible languages (e.g. Solidity) and non-EVM languages (e.g. Rust, Aptos Move, Sui Move, and Starknet Cairo). We also ensure generation tasks cover multiple languages to compare similarly difficult tasks.
4. **Difficulty Calibration** – Our benchmark includes generation tasks of wide-ranging difficulty. We assigned each task an expected difficulty rating prior to testing to examine how performance differences correlate with our expectations.
5. **Translation Comparison** – We intentionally include groups of translation tasks with the same functionality across different chains. This helps reduce confounding from task difficulty when examining performance differences by target language.
6. **Harness Ablations** – We use both a standard harness (Terminus 2) and a preferred harness (Codex CLI, Claude Code) to obtain standard model metrics and high-performance metrics on tasks.
7. **Leakage Checks** – Our task input omits the function implementation in the target contract with a *TODO* message. After each run, we performed two checks for obvious leakage. First, we examined job history metadata (e.g. token usage) to confirm that the smart contract code was generated during the run. Second, we compared the generated contract against the solution contract to check that it was not directly copied.
8. **Benchmark Integrity and Reproducibility** – We release the general task specifications and structure for each ChainBench task. We do not currently release the full verification suites used for final scoring, because public evaluators can quickly become targets for benchmark-specific fine-tuning. Final benchmark scores are therefore computed with a private verifier.

Figure 1. Overview of the ChainBench task workflow.

4. Task and Dataset Construction

4.1. Overview

ChainBench consists of 42 tasks covering smart contract operations of varying difficulty. They range from simple burn functions to complex treasury operations. 31 of these tasks are translation tasks and 11 are generation tasks. Our translation tasks cover five languages: EVM Solidity, NEAR Rust, Aptos Move, Sui Move, and Starknet Cairo. While Solana also uses Rust, we focused on testing more niche blockchains. This was to examine how models behave on chains with less development and less documentation.

In both categories, we provide context that comprehensively describes the intended functionality of the smart contract, similar to the methodology in SolContractEval (Ye et al., 2026). These are provided as "Instruction.md" files, which include information such as requirements, contract specifications, and output instructions. Two sample files are provided in Appendix D and Appendix E.

For translation tasks, we also provide a reference contract as context in which the model is supposed to translate the correctly implemented function in another language.

4.2. Task Components

Each task has four components which work together to form the task: the Instruction Prompt, the Contract Environment, the Containerized Environment, and the Verification Suite.

1. **Instruction Prompt** – A markdown file with a structured specification describing the function or contract to implement. As recommended in SolContractEval (Ye et al., 2026), this robustly describes both the envi-

ronment and intended behavior for the contract.

2. **Contract Environment** – A complete project with all dependencies required for contract functionality. For translation tasks, this includes a partially completed target contract that mirrors the solution contract but omits the implementation for the generation task.
3. **Containerized Environment** – A Docker Image to create the required environment for the task. We impose variable time constraints depending on the complexity of the task to accommodate difficult tasks.
4. **Verification Suite** – A suite of tests designed to evaluate the target contract’s functionality. The generated contract runs against these tests to determine the score for the task.

4.3. Task Workflow

For each task, we follow the procedure shown in Figure 1. To validate that the build environment is correct, we execute this process twice. First, we run the test suite on our solution contract, proceeding if all tests pass (score = 1). Then, we generate portions of the target contract using the tested model and evaluate on our testing suite.

4.4. Dataset

Each of our 42 tasks contains its own testing environment. For translation tasks, we sourced both reference contracts and solution contracts from Circle’s open-source releases. Our generation tasks were modeled after OpenZeppelin (OpenZeppelin, 2026) contracts, which served as the solution contracts for generation tasks. This strategy ensured

all tasks represented enterprise-grade blockchain development, including working with complex dependencies and real-world edge cases.

We created the target contracts by removing portions of the solution contract corresponding to the generation task. We created the instructions with the assistance of Claude Opus-4.6 (Anthropic, 2025) to give models robust context for the problem, editing the instruction files to best fit the tasks. We also manually inspected the instruction files to ensure that they did not contain solution code to reduce leakage risk.

Each task includes a testing suite with all relevant public unit tests for the solution contracts. Since the model generates only a portion of the smart contract, we only included tests where the generated functions were tested. For example, the burn and mint tasks were tested only on contract tests involving a burn or mint operation. We did this to prevent inflating the benchmark scores. Otherwise, the generated contract would always pass tests which were not related to the task, thereby increasing the score.

4.5. Difficulty Ratings

Prior to running our testing suite, we assigned each of our 42 tasks a difficulty score. These ratings were based on the smart contract behavior required, not just the amount of code the model had to write.

Easy tasks tended to involve isolated contract features, including blocklists, simple fee configuration, pausability, and deniability. These usually require a small amount of local state and one clear authorization rule.

Medium tasks introduced more stateful behavior. For example, ownership transfer and mint allowances require the model to preserve invariants across multiple actors and state transitions. These are still bounded modules, but mistakes in ordering or authorization can change the security properties of the contract.

Hard tasks combined several of these concerns at once. These tasks require models to coordinate multiple modules. Implementing a full smart contract either from a specification or by translating it from a different blockchain falls under this category. In these cases, success depends less on writing a recognizable contract pattern and more on preserving the full security model across many interacting pieces.

5. Evaluation

5.1. Environment

We ran all evaluations using the Harbor Framework (Harbor Framework Team, 2026), which standardizes model invocation and test execution. To replicate typical software development, we used the default model decoding param-

eters (i.e. temperature, max tokens, etc.) with the Harbor standard timeout. We performed all generations zero-shot with Pass@1 for a single run.

5.2. Metrics

Our primary metric is task pass rate in the target contract environment. Each test provided a binary outcome depending on the contract’s behavior. A model-generated contract received a 1 if it passed all tests and 0 if it failed one of the tests or did not compile. Model responses that timed out were also scored as 0.

5.3. Models and Harnesses

We evaluated 7 frontier models commonly used for industry-grade software development. Three models were closed-source: gpt-5.3-codex (Singh et al., 2025), claude-opus-4.6 (Anthropic, 2025), and gemini-3.1-pro (Google DeepMind, 2026); and four models were open-weight: kimi-k2.5 (Team et al., 2026), glm-4.7 (Team et al., 2025), minimax-m2.5 (MiniMax, 2026), qwen3.5-122b (Qwen Team, 2026). Given the importance of open-source software in blockchain development, we chose this mix to see how strong open-weight models could perform relative to closed-source models and compared relevant statistics to this effect. To run the tasks, we evaluated all models under Terminus 2 as a standardized same-harness setting. Where a model-specific first-party coding agent was available, we additionally evaluated that deployed preferred harness (Codex CLI for gpt-5.3-codex and Claude Code for claude-opus-4.6). We therefore report both standardized same-harness results and deployed model-agent system results. No model weights were modified throughout our experiments and all inference was run solely within the model harness with no additional tooling or access to web search.

6. Results

6.1. Leaderboard

Across our 42 tasks, we obtained the following results for successfully completed model runs. We report these in Table 1 below. This includes both standardized same-harness runs and preferred-harness runs where available, so we interpret it as a comparison of deployed model-agent systems rather than base models alone. Among the deployed systems we evaluated, gpt-5.3-codex with the Codex harness performed best.

Interestingly, claude-opus-4.6 with the Terminus 2 harness ranked second, ahead of runs with Anthropic’s Claude Code harness; but gpt-5.3-codex scored considerably worse with the Terminus 2 harness. We suspect this may be due to the system prompt differences between the two harnesses.

Codex’s system prompt is considerably longer and more detailed than Terminus 2. Other features of the harness may have impacted model runs; however, this seemed to be the most significant difference in light of the performance gain with claude-opus-4.6 using Terminus 2.

After that, gpt-5.3-codex with Terminus 2 scored similarly to gemini-3.1-pro, kimi-k2.5, glm-4.7, and minimax-m2.5 under the same harness, while qwen3.5-122b scored the worst.

Model	Tasks	Success Rate (%)	Average Time
gpt-5.3-codex (Codex CLI)	42	88.1 (75.0-94.8)	2 min, 44 sec
gpt-5.3-codex (Terminus 2)	42	59.5 (44.5-73.0)	9 min, 30 sec
claude-opus-4.6 (Claude Code)	42	73.8 (58.9-84.7)	9 min, 50 sec
claude-opus-4.6 (Terminus 2)	42	78.6 (64.1-88.3)	7 min, 00 sec
gemini-3.1-pro (Terminus 2)	42	59.5 (44.5-73.0)	3 min, 20 sec
kimi-k2.5 (Terminus 2)	42	59.5 (44.5-73.0)	14 min, 18 sec
glm-4.7 (Terminus 2)	42	57.1 (42.2-70.9)	20 min, 51 sec
minimax-m2.5 (Terminus 2)	42	52.4 (37.7-66.6)	15 min, 33 sec
qwen3.5-122b (Terminus 2)	39	38.5 (24.9-54.1)	15 min, 15 sec

Table 1. Zero-shot ChainBench scores for deployed model-agent systems. Terminus 2 rows provide a standardized same-harness comparison; Codex CLI and Claude Code rows show additional preferred-harness results where available. Qwen completed 39/42 task runs; all other systems completed 42/42.

Solving time varied widely between model types. Open-weight models had longer agent execution runs than the closed-source models.

6.2. Performance by Target Chain

Breaking down the aggregate task success among models by the language of the target contract, we obtained the results in Figure 2.

Tasks written in NEAR Rust score best, followed by EVM Solidity and Starknet Cairo. Aptos Move and Sui Move tasks had lower pass rates in our benchmark. Because many tasks replicate the same underlying functionality across different target languages, these differences are consistent with target-language effects rather than only differences in aggregate task difficulty. One possible explanation is that Aptos Move and Sui Move are less represented in model training

data and the broader online code ecosystem, though other task-specific factors may also contribute.

Figure 2. Task success rate by language of target contract.

It is possible that some differences still reflect underlying task difficulty, but many of the 42 tasks replicate the same functionality across different chains. In fact, the only “easy” task failed by a majority of the models was blacklist-evm-to-aptos. On all other blacklist translation tests at least 5 of the 7 models passed, further suggesting that target language is an important factor in benchmark performance.

Model	Aptos Move	EVM Solidity	NEAR Rust	Starknet Cairo	Sui Move
gpt-5.3-codex (Codex CLI)	85.7%	87.5%	100.0%	87.5%	84.6%
gpt-5.3-codex (Terminus 2)	71.4%	62.5%	66.7%	37.5%	61.5%
claude-opus-4.6 (Claude Code)	85.7%	62.5%	83.3%	75.0%	69.2%
claude-opus-4.6 (Terminus 2)	85.7%	87.5%	83.3%	87.5%	61.5%
gemini-3.1-pro (Terminus 2)	71.4%	75.0%	50.0%	62.5%	46.2%
kimi-k2.5 (Terminus 2)	42.9%	75.0%	83.3%	75.0%	38.5%
glm-4.7 (Terminus 2)	42.9%	50.0%	83.3%	62.5%	53.8%
minimax-m2.5 (Terminus 2)	42.9%	50.0%	66.7%	62.5%	46.2%
qwen3.5-122b (Terminus 2)	0.0%	37.5%	66.7%	37.5%	50.0%

Table 2. Pass rate (%) by model-agent system and target chain.

In Table 2, we break this down by model. We see that target language subscore trends generally mirror overall success rates. Interestingly, some models tend to struggle on tasks in certain languages (e.g. qwen3.5-122b with Aptos Move, gemini-3.1-pro with NEAR Rust). The reason for this is unclear, though differences in training exposure may be one

contributing factor.

6.3. Performance by Expected Difficulty

Prior to running our experiments, we grouped each task into an expected difficulty category of easy, medium, or hard. This was based on a number of factors including external dependencies, operation complexity, and task size. To ensure a fair comparison, no ratings were changed after obtaining the model results.

Figure 3. Task success rate by model type and difficulty.

As shown in Figure 3, task success rates were inversely correlated with task difficulty. This was especially prevalent among open-weight models, which struggled more with complex tasks. A model-by-model breakdown can be found in Appendix B.

We also examined pass rate and majority pass rate (5 out of 9 model-agent pairs) by task difficulty. These numbers were close, suggesting that models were broadly able to solve problems that were similarly challenging. In the Hard category, individual model runs of tasks passed more frequently than the number of tasks for which a majority of models passed. This could suggest that using multiple models could provide greater coverage of complex tasks, even if most fail at specific tasks.

Difficulty	Tasks	Trials	Pass (%)	Tasks with Majority Pass (%)
Easy	11	99	90.9	90.9
Medium	8	72	73.6	87.5
Hard	23	204	46.1	47.8
All	42	375	63.2	66.7

Table 3. Task success and majority pass rate by difficulty.

6.4. Performance by Task Category

Because translation tasks provide a reference implementation and generation tasks do not, we anticipated higher solve rates on translation tasks.

Figure 4. Task success rate by model type and task category.

As expected, Figure 4 shows that models achieved higher pass rates on translation tasks than on generation tasks in our benchmark setting. This may reflect the additional context provided to translation tasks, but it may also reflect differences in task source and difficulty. Our generation tasks were also rated slightly more difficult and were drawn from a different source pool (OpenZeppelin vs. Circle).

Unlike the task difficulty, the performance in open-weight and closed-source models remained consistent between task categories. One notable exception is claude-opus-4.6 with the Claude Code harness, which had a dramatic solve rate gain of 26% with the translation tasks. A breakdown by model can be found in Appendix C.

6.5. Error Analysis

To better understand model failures beyond aggregate pass rate, we inspected the verifier output for 139 failed model-task trials in our evaluation. We used claude-opus-4.6 and gpt-5.4-high to initially label and assess each failure. We then manually reviewed all failures, paying particular attention to cases where the two assistants showed even minor disagreement.

These failures split into two broad categories: *compile failures*, where the generated package did not build against the target environment, and *test failures*, where the package built successfully but violated one or more behavioral requirements. This distinction reveals a clear difference between the strongest models and the rest of the field: gpt-5.3-codex with the Codex CLI and claude-opus-4.6 with both harnesses usually failed only after reaching the test stage, while mid-table models and open-weight models lost substantially more mass before testing even began, especially on lower-resource target ecosystems.

Among frontier models, many failures were narrow misses rather than large implementation gaps. All four of gpt-5.3-codex hard test failures with the Codex CLI passed more than 80% of the verification suite, and four of seven claude-opus-4.6 test failures with the Claude Code harness were

similarly close. These near-misses were dominated by three recurring patterns. First, models often omitted defensive edge-case guards, such as rejecting zero-amount stake or unstake operations in oz-staking-vault, or checking that a removed minter was previously set in treasury-evm-to-aptos. Second, some solutions implemented the correct logic with the wrong error code or assertion ordering, as in cctp-attester-manager-evm-to-sui. Third, models sometimes missed cross-cutting restrictions that should apply uniformly across methods, such as blocking calls to the approve function while the contract is paused in oz-erc20-pausable. For smart contract systems, these are precisely the kinds of errors that determine whether an implementation is safe to ship.

Open-weight models exhibited a different failure profile. Their failures concentrated in Aptos Move, Sui Move, and Starknet Cairo, where generated code more often contained incompatible module layouts, type errors, missing interfaces, or incorrect function signatures. However, conditional on compiling, these models were often not far from correctness: several failures still passed most of the test suite. These models often appeared to understand the task, and their implementation attempts were directionally correct, but they were unable to consistently produce buildable, repository-compatible code under unfamiliar language and blockchain constraints.

The universally failed tasks reinforce these observations. Tasks such as spec-to-cctp-sui, cctp-noskel-receive-tokenctl-evm-to-sui, minter-management-evm-to-starknet, oz-staking-vault, and treasury-evm-to-aptos all require coordinating multiple subsystems, preserving minor invariants, and working with limited scaffolding in lower-resource languages. Overall, the gap exposed by ChainBench is best understood as a combination of two capabilities: reliably producing code that builds for the target chain, and closing the final semantic edge cases required for full test-suite correctness.

6.6. Harness Ablations

We observed a large harness effect for gpt-5.3-codex but not for claude-opus-4.6. Opus performed similarly under Claude Code and Terminus 2, with small task-level differences that appear consistent with single-run stochasticity and near-miss failures. In contrast, gpt-5.3-codex dropped from $\frac{37}{42}$ with Codex CLI to $\frac{25}{42}$ with Terminus 2, a 28.6% percentage-point decline.

Trajectory inspection suggests this gap is systematic. Codex-on-Terminus showed two recurring failure modes. First, some runs terminated too early after writing code or after only shallow validation. For example, on oz-erc20-pausable, Terminus 2 wrote the contract, printed it, and marked complete without running tests; the verifier later failed because

approve was not pause-gated. Second, on harder tasks, Terminus 2 entered long compile-fix loops that consumed very large token budgets but failed to converge, e.g. 400-500+ steps on several Sui/NEAR generation tasks.

Other failures were subtler: Terminus 2 often passed the package tests it ran during the trajectory, then failed additional checks in the task verifier around initialization, admin transfer, or edge-case behavior. Native Codex trajectories generally showed more repository exploration, reference-code inspection, structured patching, and explicit build/test validation before stopping.

These results suggest that ChainBench measures model-agent systems, not base models alone. For Codex in particular, the first-party harness appears to provide important behavioral scaffolding around persistence, validation, and recovery. Future work should isolate this by rerunning affected tasks with multiple seeds, adding Codex-style validation instructions to Terminus 2, and separately ablating structured edit tools such as apply_patch.

7. Benchmark Validation

7.1. Validation Scope

ChainBench is intended to measure functional correctness for cross-chain smart contract translation and generation in realistic, industry-grade development settings. We therefore validate ChainBench primarily along three axes:

1. **Harness correctness and reliability** – task environments provide authentic development contexts that are judged by executable tests which can be reproduced under repeated execution.
2. **Benchmark behavior** – task difficulty annotations and task categories behave as expected within the benchmark and compared to closely related benchmarks.
3. **Bias mitigation** – factors influencing benchmark scores from task sourcing and evaluation methodology are minimized.

Consistent with this scope, we evaluate: the solutions were authentically generated by the models (Section 7.2), the alignment between expected difficulty ratings and observed performance (Section 7.3), the relationship between ChainBench results and closely related benchmarks (Section 7.4), and potential confounds including agent/harness differences (Section 7.5), instruction-author effects (Section 7.6), and source-domain bias (Section 7.7).

We emphasize that ChainBench does not aim to be a universal measure of all smart-contract engineering. Rather, we interpret ChainBench scores as reflecting the ability of

model-agent systems to produce working contract code that satisfies repository-level test suites for industry-grade development across multiple target chains and toolchains.

7.2. Solution Validity

After each task run, we manually verified that the patch applied to the target contract corresponded to model-generated code implementing the specified functions, rather than a leaked reference solution. Our harness constrains the agent to edit only the designated regions of the target contract (e.g., *TODO* blocks) and does not provide direct access to overwrite files, which simplifies inspection and reduces the risk of accidental solution injection. Examples of a solution script and pre-implementation target contract are provided in Appendix F and Appendix G, respectively. This allowed us to easily verify generated solutions and further prevent leakage.

7.3. Difficulty Validity

As discussed, our pre-evaluation expected difficulty ratings were generally consistent with model performance. The variance within groups could potentially be attributed to target contract language. For example, the observed NEAR Rust tasks were broadly solvable despite difficulty ratings, but even easy tasks in Aptos Move gave models trouble.

7.4. Consistency with Related Benchmarks

The closest benchmarks to ChainBench are SolContractEval (Ye et al., 2026) and SolEval (Peng et al., 2025), but our evaluation scope is slightly different. ChainBench evaluates top-of-the-line models with harnesses, while SolContractEval and SolEval evaluated older models with smaller parameter sizes. They also do not use a container harness like ChainBench does. Therefore, we conduct a qualitative convergence validity check by comparing the results of ChainBench to SolContractEval and SolEval.

Similar to ChainBench, both SolContractEval and SolEval reported a strong performance from closed-source models relative to open-weight models. SolContractEval also saw the gemini model family perform the worst of the closed-source models. Unlike ChainBench, however, claude-sonnet-3.7 slightly outperformed o4-mini for Pass@1 on their benchmark, while gpt-5.3-codex with the Codex CLI performed better than claude-opus-4.6 under Pass@1 scoring on ChainBench. Still, the difference is fairly small with the GPT and Claude model families performing best on both benchmarks.

7.5. Agentic Bias

Consistent with the goal of evaluating the performance of models on industry-grade smart contract development, we

evaluated all model-agent systems as deployed tools. This could introduce a bias depending on whether the Codex CLI agent, Claude Code, or Terminus 2 harness were used. While there were significant differences for gpt-5.3-codex depending on the harness, results were relatively similar for claude-opus-4.6 between Terminus 2 and Claude Code. It’s possible that other models could experience similar performance gains when using a specialized harness; however, these were not available at the time of our experiment.

7.6. Instructor-Author Bias

As previously discussed, instruction files were generated with the assistance of claude-opus-4.6. This potentially introduces a risk of instructor-author bias. However, we note that claude-opus-4.6 was not the top-performing system in our evaluation. This suggests that such an advantage, while potentially present, is unlikely to dominate the leaderboard. Still, this is a potential limitation of the benchmark and could inflate the results for claude-opus-4.6.

7.7. Source Bias

All translation tasks were sourced from Circle’s open-source releases. While this was done to ensure a fair comparison across target contract languages in the context of industry-grade smart contract development, it could introduce a bias towards Circle-related operations. That being said, these tasks are both diverse in scope and common operations in the blockchain space (e.g. Mint/Burn). Additionally, we generally observed similar performance across the models for the translation tasks as we did for the generation tasks, which were sourced from OpenZeppelin. If this had introduced bias towards specific models, we would have likely seen a more pronounced difference in performance between the models than in the generation tasks. Still, because translation and generation tasks were drawn from different source pools, comparisons between task categories should also be interpreted with caution. The tasks chosen may represent a subset of the blockchain space and do not explicitly cover all development, especially on non-industry use cases.

8. Conclusion

8.1. Limitations & Changes

There are a number of limitations to ChainBench and changes that could be made to improve the benchmark:

1. **Use a mixture of models to generate instructions** – This would help alleviate the potential instructor-author bias introduced by using Opus-4.6 to generate instructions. To measure the whole generation process, future work may want to generate the instructions with the model being tested.

2. **Conduct Pass@k evaluations to test full model capabilities** – While we ran Pass@1 evaluations to best simulate the developer experience, future work may want to conduct Pass@k evaluations to test full model capabilities.
3. **Include translation and generation tasks from more diverse sources** – Drawing tasks from more sources would allow the benchmark to better represent all of industry-grade smart contract development. Future work may want to include tasks from verified contracts on-chain as well as testing suites for cross-chain platforms. Tasks in uncommon languages as well as more translation tasks between them should also be included for robustness.
4. **Contamination risk** – Although web search was disabled for the model-agent systems, it is possible that the models were trained on this data given the public nature of our tests and solution contracts. Future work may want to use a more secure way to test the models; however, this may be difficult considering the open-source nature of blockchain technology.

8.2. Takeaways

While there are a number of limitations to ChainBench, our results suggest four key takeaways for industry-grade smart contract development with LLMs:

1. **Frontier models can implement industry-grade contracts, but miss edge-case protections** – While observed performance was not perfect, models were able to produce working contract code that satisfies repository-level test suites for industry-grade development across multiple target chains and toolchains. Even tasks that were expected to be difficult could be solved by frontier models; and when misses happened, they were often minor edge cases. Open-weight models contained more significant errors; however, they were able to successfully build many of the easier tasks.
2. **Translation tasks had higher pass rates than generation tasks** – Models scored higher on translation tasks than on raw generation tasks. Because the two categories also differ in available context, expected difficulty, and task sourcing, we interpret this as evidence that providing a reference contract can help in this benchmark setting rather than as a clean causal advantage of translation over generation. Still, the difference is notable.
3. **Target contract language affects performance** – Pass rates differed across target contract languages, including on groups of tasks with matched functionality across chains. This pattern may reflect differences

in language familiarity, available training data, and ecosystem maturity. Developers working in lower-resource languages may need to provide more context to models or use systems with stronger support for the target ecosystem.

4. **Industry-grade smart contract benchmarks should evaluate model + agent combinations** – We saw a considerable jump in performance for gpt-5.3-codex when using the Codex harness versus Terminus 2. Given that modern smart contract development makes use of agentic tools, this could justify evaluating agent + model harness combinations as opposed to all models in the same harness.

8.3. Broader Impacts

Our results suggest that frontier models can already produce working smart-contract code on some tasks. On simpler tasks, several systems completed implementations that satisfied repository-level verification suites. However, as task complexity increased, failures increasingly took the form of near-misses: code that passed core tests but failed edge cases, authorization checks, or other security-relevant conditions.

This pattern calls for caution. Blockchain failures rarely arise in the happy path. Instead, they arise at the boundaries, in unexpected interactions, and under adversarial pressure. Smart contracts that appear correct but fail under these conditions may create a false sense of security, particularly in public blockchain systems where deployed code is transparent and financially exposed. For this reason, partial correctness is not enough.

ChainBench is intended to help make these strengths and limitations visible. By identifying where current model-agent systems are reliable and where they remain brittle, the benchmark can support safer use of LLMs in smart-contract development. As blockchain infrastructure and model capabilities continue to evolve, benchmarks should evolve with them. We therefore view ChainBench as a living benchmark that can help guide progress toward internet financial infrastructure that is safer, more transparent, and more reliable.

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A. Appendix: Full Results by Task and Model

Task	gpt-5.3-codex (Codex/T2)	claude-opus-4.6 (Claude Code/T2)	gemini-3.1-pro (T2)	kimi-k2.5 (T2)	glm-4.7 (T2)	minimax-m2.5 (T2)	qwen3.5-122b (T2)
Easy Tasks							
blocklist-evm-to-near	✓/✓	✓/✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
blocklist-evm-to-sui	✓/✓	✓/✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
denylistable-evm-to-starknet	✓/✓	✓/✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
erc20-solidity	✓/✓	✓/✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
mint-allowance-evm-to-sui	✓/✓	✓/✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
oz-erc20-solidity	✓/✓	✓/✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
pausable-evm-to-starknet	✓/✓	✓/✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
pausable-evm-to-sui	✓/✓	✓/✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
pausable-evm-to-aptos	✓/✓	✓/✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗
blocklist-evm-to-starknet	✓/✓	✓/✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗
blocklist-evm-to-aptos	✓/✗	✓/✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
Medium Tasks							
mint-burn-evm-to-near	✓/✓	✓/✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
ownable-evm-to-starknet	✓/✗	✓/✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
roles-evm-to-sui	✓/✓	✓/✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
cctp-attester-evm-to-aptos	✓/✓	✓/✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗
upgradeable-evm-to-starknet	✓/✗	✓/✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗
manageable-evm-to-starknet	✓/✗	✓/✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗
cctp-attester-manager-evm-to-sui	✗/✓	✓/✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗
oz-erc20-pausable	✓/✗	✗/✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗
Hard Tasks							
cctp-deposit-for-burn-evm-to-sui	✓/✗	✓/✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
full-treasury-evm-to-near-integ	✓/✓	✓/✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
cctp-token-messenger-evm-to-aptos	✓/✓	✓/✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗
full-treasury-evm-to-near	✓/✓	✓/✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓
oz-governor-dao	✓/✓	✓/✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓
spec-to-stablecoin-evm	✓/✓	✓/✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗
cctp-message-transmitter-evm-to-aptos	✓/✓	✓/✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗
mint-burn-evm-to-sui	✓/✓	✓/✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	—
spec-to-stablecoin-near	✓/✗	✓/✓	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗
cctp-full-message-transmitter-evm-to-aptos	✓/✓	✓/✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗
oz-erc4626-vault	✓/✗	✗/✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗
spec-to-cctp-evm	✓/✓	✓/✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗
cctp-send-receive-evm-to-sui	✓/✓	✓/✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	—
metadata-evm-to-starknet	✓/✗	✗/✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗
noskel-treasury-evm-to-sui	✓/✗	✓/✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	—
full-treasury-evm-to-sui	✓/✓	✗/✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
noskel-treasury-evm-to-near	✓/✗	✗/✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
spec-to-stablecoin-sui	✓/✗	✗/✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
spec-to-cctp-sui	✓/✗	✗/✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
cctp-noskel-receive-tokenctl-evm-to-sui	✗/✗	✗/✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
minter-management-evm-to-starknet	✗/✗	✗/✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
oz-staking-vault	✗/✗	✗/✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
treasury-evm-to-aptos	✗/✗	✗/✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗

Table 4. Per-task outcomes by model. ✓ pass, ✗ fail, — unsuccessful run. In the gpt-5.3-codex and claude-opus-4.6 headers, a slash between marks indicates running tasks with the native harness or with Terminus 2 (T2).

B. Appendix: Model Performance by Task Difficulty

C. Appendix: Model Performance by Task Category

D. Appendix: Sample Translation Task Instruction File

```

# Blocklist: EVM (Solidity) to Sui Move Translation

## Task

The `treasury.move` file is missing `blocklist` and `unblocklist` functions. Implement them so the tests pass.

**Important:** Write your changes to `/app/sources/treasury.move` (not `/app/packages/stablecoin/sources/`).
The test harness copies files from `/app/sources/` into the package before building.

## Source: EVM Solidity (Blacklistable.sol)

```solidity
pragma solidity 0.6.12;

import { Ownable } from "./Ownable.sol";

abstract contract Blacklistable is Ownable {
 address public blacklist;
 mapping(address => bool) internal _deprecatedBlacklisted;

 event Blacklisted(address indexed _account);
 event UnBlacklisted(address indexed _account);
 event BlacklistChanged(address indexed newBlacklist);

 modifier onlyBlacklist() {
 require(msg.sender == blacklist, "caller is not the blacklist");
 _;
 }

 modifier notBlacklisted(address _account) {
 require(!_isBlacklisted(_account), "account is blacklisted");
 _;
 }

 function isBlacklisted(address _account) external view returns (bool) {
 return _isBlacklisted(_account);
 }

 function blacklist(address _account) external onlyBlacklist {
 _blacklist(_account);
 emit Blacklisted(_account);
 }

 function unBlacklist(address _account) external onlyBlacklist {
 _unBlacklist(_account);
 emit UnBlacklisted(_account);
 }

 function updateBlacklist(address _newBlacklist) external onlyOwner {
 require(_newBlacklist != address(0), "new blacklist is the zero address");
 blacklist = _newBlacklist;
 emit BlacklistChanged(blacklist);
 }

 function _isBlacklisted(address _account) internal virtual view returns (bool);
 function _blacklist(address _account) internal virtual;
 function _unBlacklist(address _account) internal virtual;
}
```

The full EVM codebase is available at `/app/stablecoin-evm/contracts/` for additional reference.

## Target Context

In Sui Move, the stablecoin uses Sui's native `DenyList` mechanism instead of a simple mapping for blocklisting.
Look at the existing functions in `treasury.move` (like `pause` and `unpause`) to understand the patterns used.

The full Sui codebase is at `/app/packages/stablecoin/`.

## Testing

```bash
cp /app/sources/treasury.move /app/packages/stablecoin/sources/
cd /app/packages/stablecoin && sui move test
```

```

E. Appendix: Sample Generation Task Instruction File

```
Generate a complete ERC20 token contract in Solidity.

## Requirements

- Implement the full ERC20 interface:
  - `name()`, `symbol()`, `decimals()`
  - `totalSupply()`, `balanceOf(address)`
  - `transfer(address to, uint256 amount)`
  - `approve(address spender, uint256 amount)`
  - `allowance(address owner, address spender)`
  - `transferFrom(address from, address to, uint256 amount)`
- Include `mint` and `burn` functions (onlyOwner for mint)
- Use OpenZeppelin-style patterns but do NOT import external libraries
- Include proper events: `Transfer`, `Approval`
- Use Solidity ^0.8.0
- Include basic access control (owner pattern)

## Contract Specifications

- Contract name: `SimpleToken`
- Token name: "Simple Token"
- Token symbol: "SMPL"
- Decimals: 18
- Initial supply: 1,000,000 tokens minted to deployer

## Output

Save your implementation to `/app/src/SimpleToken.sol`
```

F. Appendix: Sample Generated Solution Script

```
# Replace the stubbed mint function with the correct implementation
sed -i 's/todo!("Implement mint")/require!(!self.paused, "FiatToken: paused");\
require_only(Role:Minter);\
let caller_id: AccountId = env::predecessor_account_id();\
require_not_blocklisted(&caller_id);\
require_not_blocklisted(&to);\
require!(amount.0 > 0, "FiatToken: mint amount not greater than 0");\
\
let new_minter_allowance: u128 = self\
    .minter_allowed\
    .get(&env::predecessor_account_id())\
    .unwrap_or(&U128::from(0))\
    .0\
    .checked_sub(amount.0)\
    .unwrap_or_else(|| env::panic_str("FiatToken: mint amount exceeds minter allowance"));

self.token.internal_deposit(&to, Balance::from(amount));

self.minter_allowed\
    .insert(caller_id, U128::from(new_minter_allowance));

near_contract_standards::fungible_token::events::FtMint {\
    owner_id: &to,\
    amount: &amount,\
    memo: None,\
}\
.emit();' /app/src/ft_token.rs

# Replace the stubbed burn function with the correct implementation
sed -i 's/todo!("Implement burn")/require!(!self.paused, "FiatToken: paused");\
require_only(Role:Minter);\
let caller_id: AccountId = env::predecessor_account_id();\
require_not_blocklisted(&caller_id);\
require!(amount.0 > 0, "FiatToken: burn amount not greater than 0");\
\
let minter_balance: U128 = self.ft_balance_of(caller_id.clone());\
require!(\
    minter_balance >= amount,\
    "FiatToken: burn amount exceeds balance"\
);\

self.token\
    .internal_withdraw(&caller_id, Balance::from(amount));

near_contract_standards::fungible_token::events::FtBurn {\
    owner_id: &caller_id,\
    amount: &amount,\
    memo: None,\
}\
.emit();' /app/src/ft_token.rs
```

G. Appendix: Sample Target Contract Prior to Implementation

```
/// Mints tokens via internal_deposit and emits an FtMint event.
/// Validates that caller is a minter and that neither the caller nor the to account
/// are blacklisted.
/// * `to` - The address that will receive the minted tokens.
/// * `amount` - The amount of tokens to mint. Must be less than or equal
/// to the minter_allowance of the caller.
pub fn mint(&mut self, to: AccountId, amount: U128) {
    todo!("Implement mint")
}

/// Burns tokens via internal_withdraw and emits an FtBurn event.
/// Validates that caller is a minter.
/// * `amount` - The amount of tokens to burn. Must be less than or equal
/// to the minter's account balance.
pub fn burn(&mut self, amount: U128) {
    todo!("Implement burn")
}
```